

**CLIMATE RESILIENCE ENHANCEMENT IN DAIRY FARMING:
CLIRESDAIRY PROJECT STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP
WORKSHOP REPORT**

Date: 24/12/2025

Location: Aydın, Türkiye

Project Lead Organisation: Cattle Breeders' Association of Aydın

Event name: CLIMAAX – CliResDairy Project Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

Moderators:

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- Prof. Dr. Renan Tunalıoğlu, Faculty members of the Department of Agricultural Economics at Aydın Adnan Menderes University)
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Reporters:

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1. Introduction

Within the scope of the CliResDairy Project, supported under the Horizon Europe CLIMAAX Programme, a stakeholder workshop was held in Aydin Province on 24 December 2025.

The objective of the workshop was to identify the current vulnerabilities of dairy cattle farms to climate hazards through local knowledge and field-based experiences; to evaluate the impacts of these risks on production systems through multi-stakeholder discussions; and to systematically collect feasible adaptation options.

The workshop was organized in the form of three parallel roundtable sessions. Each table focused on two main discussion themes: “current risks and challenges” and “actions and solution proposals.” In alignment with the climate hazards prioritized under the project, three thematic areas were addressed at the tables:

- Impacts of Extreme Heatwave on Livestock Production
- Drought, Water Management and Feed Systems
- Extreme Precipitation, Flood Risk and Farm Infrastructure

2. Goal and Scope

The workshop aimed to achieve the following objectives:

- To identify risk and problem areas in dairy cattle farming related to climate hazards, based on field-level evidence;
- To determine shared and recurring vulnerabilities across dimensions such as production, infrastructure, the feed–water–energy nexus, and animal health and welfare;
- To categorize feasible actions and solution proposals within a framework of technical, administrative, and financial instruments;
- To establish a field-based reference framework to inform project activities and future outputs.

3. Methodology

The workshop was conducted using a structured qualitative data collection approach.

3.1. Work Schedule

The discussions were conducted around three separate tables, with each table facilitated by a moderator and supported by a reporter.

- Each table addressed the three thematic topics under two subheadings: “current risks and challenges” and “actions and proposed solutions.”
- Moderators shared preliminary findings and insights gathered from pre-workshop interviews with farmers; these were then expanded upon with the experiences and suggestions of the participants.
- All issues raised at the tables were systematically documented by the reporters.

3.2. Compilation and Merging Process

- The notes collected from the three tables were consolidated under a common thematic framework.
- Repetitive statements conveying the same content were grouped under single headings, while preserving the unique technical details that emerged at each table.
- The findings were structured to first present the identification of risks and challenges, followed by proposed solutions organized into strategic sets.

4. PARTICIPANT PROFILE

A total of 124 participants attended the stakeholder engagement workshop organized under the CliResDairy Project. The participants represented a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including producers/breeders, agricultural organizations and cooperatives, public institutions, universities/academic institutions, the private sector, civil society organizations, and professional associations. The workshop ensured inclusive participation of all relevant local actors involved in dairy farming, agriculture, water management, environment, and climate-related fields.

The institutional and professional breakdown of the participants is as follows:

Dairy Producers/ Dairy Breeders

- Dairy cattle breeders, milk producers, and farmers: 58 participants

Agricultural Organizations and Cooperations: 26 participants

- Aydin Cattle Breeders’ Association (CBAA) (managers, technical staff, and member producers): 16 participants
- Cooperatives (Nazilli and Surrounding Agricultural Development, Söke Agricultural Development Cooperative): 8 participants
- National federations and agricultural unions (Central Union of Livestock Cooperatives of Türkiye, Aydin Branch of the Central Union of Livestock Cooperatives of Türkiye, Aydin Red Meat Producers’ Association): 2 participants

Public Institutions: 21 participants

- Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry provincial branches (Aydin Provincial Directorate, Efeler District Directorate): 9 participants
- Agricultural and Rural Development Support Institution (ARDSI), Aydin Office: 4 participants
- Regional Director of the 21st Regional Directorate of State Hydraulic Works: 2 participants
- Aydin Provincial Directorate of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change: 3 participants
- Provincial Directorate of Meteorology: 2 participants
- Local government (Aydin Metropolitan Municipality – Agricultural Services): 1 participant

Academic Institutions: 12 participants

- Aydin Adnan Menderes University (Faculty of Agriculture and Faculty of Veterinary Medicine): 12 participants

Private Sector and Professional Associations: 5 participants

- Representatives from agricultural machinery, dairy companies, and other private sector stakeholders: 5 participants

Civil Society Organizations: 2 participants

- Turkish Agriculturalists Association, Aydin Branch: 2 participants

5. FINDINGS

Below, the outputs from the three discussion tables are consolidated and presented without repetition.

5.1. EXTREME HEAT AND ITS EFFECTS ON ANIMAL PRODUCTION

5.1.1 Current Situation, Risks and Issues

- It was noted that the pace of global warming has exceeded previous projections; while a 1°C increase was expected over approximately 100 years in the past, recent trends show that such warming has occurred within just 30 years. As a result, impacts previously anticipated for the 2200s are already being experienced today.
- Extreme heat events were reported to cause heat stress in dairy cattle, negatively affecting animal welfare and increasing behavioral risks, including aggressive behaviors.
- Heat stress was said to elevate oxidative stress levels, leading to an increase in somatic cell counts. This rise was associated with a decline in milk fat content and other quality parameters.
- Excessive heat was identified as a key factor behind reduced milk yield, fertility rates, and dry matter intake, ultimately decreasing healthy milk production.

- The effects of heat stress are not confined to summer months; it was emphasized that cumulative stress during summer continues to impair productivity and reproductive performance in subsequent production cycles.
- A rise in viral and bacterial animal diseases was observed under extreme heat conditions, leading to overall deterioration in animal health and welfare.
- It was stated that high temperatures adversely impact not only livestock production but also crop production, causing declines in both yield and quality of forage crops.
- Increases in temperature and humidity were linked to spoilage of feed, with a higher risk of mycotoxin-producing fungi, especially between 5–20°C. Although these fungi die off above 40°C, they pose serious health risks before such temperatures are reached.
- Deficiencies in hygiene and sanitation practices were noted, especially during hot periods, which led to increased hygiene problems with farm equipment.
- Extreme heat was reported to result in labor losses, disruptions in production processes, and even tendencies among some farmers to abandon production altogether.
- Decreased production, rising costs, and withdrawal from production were identified as potential contributors to broader food access challenges.
- With increasing temperatures, energy and logistics costs have also risen, pushing up the overall cost of milk production and reducing profit margins for farms.
- It was stated that small-scale farms cannot afford energy investments (e.g., ventilation, cooling, solar power systems) on their own due to limited capital.
- Although Holstein cows, which are widely raised in the region, have high milk yield potential, they were described as genetically less resistant to high temperatures.
- Indigenous cattle breeds that are more heat-tolerant were reported to be underfed or abandoned over time, putting them at risk of extinction and increasing the sector's vulnerability to climate change.
- Finally, a widespread lack of knowledge, awareness, and training in small-scale farms was emphasized, with incorrect or incomplete information often leading to misguided investments and resource waste.

5.1.2 Actions and Proposed Solutions

- To mitigate the impacts of extreme heat on livestock production, it was emphasized that farm-specific and holistic climate control plans should be developed.
- It was proposed to design technically grounded and customized cooling solutions that consider barn orientation, location, capacity, building type, ventilation systems, wind direction, and regional climate conditions.
- Strengthening ventilation and cooling infrastructure, using evaporative cooling systems, and adding nutritional supplements to rations during heatwaves were identified as key strategies.
- Shifting feeding times to cooler parts of the day (especially evenings) and adopting heat-stress-appropriate feeding strategies were recommended.
- Reducing dependency on external feed sources and utilizing local and regional by-products such as olive pulp were suggested.
- Support was proposed for technologies such as automatic calf feeding systems and climate-resilient barn designs.
- Expanding rooftop solar panel (PV) installations, initiating collective energy investments through producer organizations, and exploring centralized renewable energy generation and distribution models for members were all recommended.
- Enhancing energy efficiency through livestock organized industrial zones and revising legal frameworks related to renewable energy were also suggested.

- Developing heat-tolerant animal breeds, supporting genetic selection, and conserving native genetic resources were identified as strategic priorities.
- It was recommended to remove low-yielding animals from herds and to restructure herd management based on climate conditions.
- Composting solid and liquid manure for soil use was considered a beneficial practice from both environmental and production standpoints.
- It was emphasized that cooperatives, collective milking facilities, and shared infrastructure could increase climate resilience, particularly for small-scale farms.
- Conducting a province-wide capacity assessment, planning farm locations systematically, and evaluating regulatory tools such as production quotas to prevent uncontrolled expansion were suggested.
- Strengthening advisory services, vocational training, and agricultural extension efforts, especially through hands-on and demonstration-based education, was proposed.
- Establishing vocational certification systems to formalize farming practices and incentivizing climate-friendly, animal-welfare-focused, and resource-efficient farms were highlighted as necessary steps.

5.2. DROUGHT, WATER MANAGEMENT AND FEED SYSTEMS

5.2.1 Current Situation, Risks and Issues

- It was emphasized that drought is no longer a temporary climate phenomenon for dairy farms but has become a structural risk factor with long-term impacts on water supply, feed production, feeding strategies, and farm economics.
- Irregularities in recent precipitation patterns, coupled with declining surface and groundwater resources, have had direct effects on the production capacity and sustainability of livestock farms.
- The need for drinking water in livestock operations has increased due to changing climate conditions, yet water quality, continuity, and access cannot be guaranteed for all farms.
- Restrictions on accessing drinking and irrigation water have direct negative effects on milk yield, fertility, and animal health.
- Due to limited access to surface water, producers increasingly rely on artesian wells and groundwater, leading to a rise in the number of such wells.
- With the growing use of groundwater for irrigation, drilling and pumping costs have increased, placing significant financial pressure on farms.
- Intensive groundwater use has also led to a decline in water quality in artesian wells.
- Despite the presence of large dams such as Adıgüzel Dam, there is a growing preference for groundwater use over surface reservoirs, which is not sustainable from a water management perspective.
- There is a need to reassess and monitor riverbeds and water collection areas, especially those with alluvial structures.
- Bureaucratic hurdles and complex permitting processes for agricultural irrigation were noted as barriers preventing timely and planned irrigation by farmers.
- Drought conditions have significantly altered forage crops, specially making water availability a critical constraint for second-season crops.
- The production of water-intensive forage crops such as silage maize is increasingly challenging, leading some producers to abandon or reduce the area of forage crop cultivation.

- In regions like the Söke Plain, soil salinity has become a key factor in determining cropping patterns, further limiting forage crop options.
- Due to water limitations and market dynamics, some producers are shifting to alternative crops like cotton or oilseed sunflower, reducing the emphasis on forage crops and increasing pressure on feed supply.
- There has been a noticeable decline in forage crop quality affecting digestibility and nutritional value.
- Poor silage quality, due to inadequate techniques and lack of labor or knowledge, was identified as a concern.
- As forage crop cultivation contracts, farms are becoming more dependent on external feed sources, increasing feeding costs and the cost per liter of milk.
- Under drought conditions, feed costs rise, ration balance is disrupted, and animal performance declines.
- In many farms, forage production and livestock operations are not fully integrated, leading to increased dependency on external feed due to land constraints, water scarcity, and small farm sizes.
- Field trials and pilot programs for drought- and salt-tolerant forage crops and seed mixtures remain limited.
- Farmers experimenting with alternative crops bear high production and income risks, which are not adequately shared through public or private risk-sharing mechanisms.
- While modern irrigation systems like drip irrigation can save water, farmers approach them cautiously due to soil structure and salinity risks. Without proper drainage and monitoring, these systems may lead to salt accumulation.
- The drought has made the water-energy nexus even more critical, with the cost of electricity used in irrigation becoming a major economic burden.
- The severity of the drought and water scarcity problem is evident in the fact that even controversial measures such as artificial rainfall are now being considered.

5.2.2 Actions and Proposed Solutions

- It emphasized that drought adaptation policies should be addressed within an integrated framework that encompasses water management, forage crop production, feeding strategies, energy costs, and production planning.
- Ensuring clean, continuous, and sufficient drinking water in livestock farms should be treated as a top priority, and practices for monitoring water quality should be expanded.
- Water harvesting and on-farm water storage systems—particularly at scales suitable for small farms—should be promoted and supported.
- The installation of rainwater harvesting systems in farms and the provision of financial support for such systems was recommended.
- The transition to pressurized, water-saving irrigation systems in agriculture should be encouraged; however, local soil structure, salinity risk, and drainage capacity must be considered in the process.
- The expansion of drip irrigation systems should be accompanied by location-specific technical guidance and monitoring mechanisms.
- Bureaucratic barriers to irrigation system modernization should be removed.
- Irrigation planning should be carried out regionally by the State Hydraulic Works (DSİ), and schedules and related information should be made available through public platforms.
- For farms dependent on groundwater irrigation, the use of renewable energy sources such as solar power (PV systems) should be supported to reduce energy costs.

- Combining shading systems to reduce evaporation with solar energy systems in water reservoirs was proposed.
- Ecological use and treatment of seawater for agricultural and potable purposes should be explored. In this context, a proposal was made to invest in a seawater desalination facility along the Didim–Söke (Balat Plain) corridor.
- The promotion and piloting of drought- and salinity-tolerant forage crops and seed mixtures (e.g., vetch, sainfoin, sorghum-sudan grass, oat + triticale + vetch + forage pea + wheat mixes) were recommended.
- It was suggested that sowing of winter forage crops, early harvesting of silage maize, and crop planning should be adjusted according to climate conditions.
- Under drought conditions, cereal-based forage crops such as wheat silage and hay should be supported.
- The selection of drought-tolerant and low-water-input forage crops should be encouraged.
- Efficient use of greywater and the strengthening of internal water reuse systems within farms were recommended.
- Research and pilot projects on alternative protein sources (e.g., insect-based feeds) should be supported within feed systems.
- Publicly owned rangelands should be used effectively and systematically to allow farms to reduce reliance on cultivated forage during certain periods.
- Forage production, livestock operations, and water availability should be evaluated together to develop region-specific production planning models.
- Risk-sharing mechanisms such as grants, insurance, and purchase guarantees should be introduced for farmers experimenting with alternative or trial crops.
- Early warning and guidance systems monitoring supply–demand dynamics in the forage market should be developed to support producer decision-making.
- Training should be provided on water management and forage production, with agricultural organizations taking a more active role in field-based farmer awareness.
- Small-scale farms should be incentivized to adopt modern agricultural technologies.

5.3. EXTREME PRECIPITATION, FLOOD RISK AND FARM INFRASTRUCTURE

5.3.1 Current Situation, Risks and Issues

- The increasing frequency and severity of extreme precipitation events have become a growing risk factor for dairy farms.
- It was emphasized that flood risk should not be assessed solely through meteorological conditions; human-induced factors such as land use decisions, lack of planning, narrowing of streambeds, and development in natural floodplains must also be considered.
- In recent years, some livestock facilities have been established near streambeds or in areas with high flood risk, creating significant exposure for both livestock and farm infrastructure.
- There have been cases of damage to farms due to flooding, and the existing disaster risk mitigation infrastructure has proven insufficient.
- Blockages in streambeds that cause sediment buildup increase flood risks, while the narrowing of streams and disruption of natural flow regimes have further intensified these risks.

- The destruction of natural vegetation and trees along streambanks has worsened the impacts of floods, resulting in uncontrolled water spread and greater damage to infrastructure.
- Planned deforestation has also contributed to flood risk, while vegetation was recognized as a key element of flood mitigation.
- The destruction of forest ecosystems and the expansion of mining activities have further increased flood risks, highlighting how land use changes, in addition to natural processes, contribute to the problem.
- Higher humidity levels and the resulting increase in mycotoxins were identified as a major risk for both animal and human health. Excessive rainfall, combined with poor storage conditions, leads to increased incidence of mycotoxin-contaminated feed.
- Flooding and extreme rainfall negatively impact feed storage, and inadequate storage infrastructure leads to losses in feed quality and poses indirect economic risks.
- The permitting and inspection mechanisms for livestock operations located in flood-prone areas are not functioning effectively. Past zoning amnesty and regulations have encouraged settlement in high-risk zones, exacerbating vulnerabilities.
- Responsibilities and mandates for flood risk management are fragmented across various public institutions, leading to gaps in planning and implementation. Lack of coordination among agencies complicates risk reduction efforts.
- Flood management entails different levels of difficulty depending on farm size. Small family farms often lack the resources and capacity to implement innovative infrastructure solutions, while medium and large farms have better access to investment opportunities.
- Farm-level measures alone are insufficient to reduce flood risks; a basin-wide and regional planning approach is necessary.
- Unpredictable timing and spatial distribution of rainfall negatively affect both crop production and livestock infrastructure.
- In areas with shallow groundwater tables, inadequate drainage infrastructure has hindered both crop and livestock activities. In some places, open drainage systems are no longer functioning effectively.
- The complete relocation of farms located in flood-prone areas is often not feasible in the short to medium term due to high costs, land tenure complexity, land availability, and social factors. Except for extremely high-risk zones, on-site risk reduction measures are considered more realistic.

5.3.2 Actions and Proposed Solutions

- Dairy farms should be classified according to flood risk levels (low-medium-high), and this classification should guide planning and permitting processes.
- New livestock facilities should not be permitted in high-risk flood zones. For existing farms, rehabilitation and structural reinforcement should be prioritized.
- Structural flood control measures: such as hilltop reservoirs, levees, and regional-scale flood control infrastructure, should be planned systematically.
- Farm-level structural solutions (e.g., perimeter bunds, elevation of critical assets) should be promoted, particularly in cases where relocation is not feasible.
- Streambed rehabilitation should be conducted to remove obstructions and restore natural flow regimes.
- In areas with high groundwater levels or intense surface water pressure, a gradual transition to closed drainage systems should be encouraged, alongside improvements to open drainage functionality.

- Rainwater harvesting should not be treated as a stand-alone solution but should be integrated with storage, redirection, and controlled discharge systems.
- When considering proposals to store freshwater near the Menderes River delta, potential ecological impacts: such as effects on fisheries, should be carefully evaluated.
- Natural vegetation in floodplains and riverbanks should be protected and rehabilitated. Reforestation and nature-based solutions should be considered part of flood risk management.
- Forest ecosystems must be conserved, and environmental sensitivities should be respected when evaluating mining permits.
- Where full relocation of flood-exposed farms is not feasible, support mechanisms should be established for on-site reinforcement and protection.
- Early warning systems, hazard monitoring infrastructure, and effective disaster prevention frameworks must be strengthened (e.g., installation of sensors in low-lying riverbed areas).
- Public communication mechanisms: such as SMS alerts and mobile applications, should be improved in high-risk areas.
- Legal frameworks for flood risk reduction should be supported by stronger enforcement and inspection mechanisms.
- Coordination among local governments, central authorities, and relevant agencies is critical for effective planning and investment.
- Although the role of individual farmers in flood mitigation is limited, awareness-raising and training can enhance preparedness.
- To reduce the risk of feed contamination (e.g., mycotoxins), concentrate feed should be stored above ground with improved conditions.
- Feed storage facilities must be reinforced against moisture and flood damage and integrated into broader risk management plans.
- Surface water pollution and groundwater infiltration, especially around the Menderes River, should be mitigated.
- Climate-resilient crops with low water demand should be promoted by local governments and public agencies.
- Public subsidies, incentives, and investments in infrastructure should prioritize flood risk mitigation strategies.